

Table S7. Univariate mixed effects logistic regression for *dhfr* and *dhps* gene mutations (pure mutants versus wild type/mixed)

Odds ratios (OR) with 95% CI and *p* values are presented (*p* values <0.05 in bold).

<i>dhfr</i>		N51				C59				S108				triple <i>dhfr</i>			
Fixed effect(s)	Samples	OR	[95% CI]		<i>p</i>	OR	[95%CI]		<i>p</i>	OR	[95%CI]		<i>p</i>	OR	[95%CI]		<i>p</i>
Age (per 10 years)	ANC	0.82	0.58	1.15	0.245	0.94	0.66	1.33	0.712	0.96	0.67	1.37	0.820	0.83	0.58	1.18	0.294
	Del	1.46	0.90	2.37	0.130	1.55	0.89	2.68	0.118	1.65	0.89	3.07	0.110	1.28	0.81	2.01	0.287
	GP	1.14	1.00	1.31	0.048	1.04	0.91	1.19	0.591	0.99	0.87	1.13	0.890	1.18	1.03	1.35	0.015
Parasitaemia (log scale)	ANC	1.11	0.88	1.39	0.390	0.92	0.73	1.17	0.502	0.93	0.73	1.17	0.521	1.14	0.91	1.44	0.260
	Del	0.77	0.59	1.00	0.047	0.85	0.64	1.13	0.263	0.87	0.64	1.19	0.389	0.80	0.62	1.01	0.055
	GP	0.85	0.68	1.06	0.150	0.87	0.70	1.09	0.229	0.93	0.74	1.16	0.494	0.77	0.62	0.97	0.026
Gravity	ANC	0.99	0.89	1.09	0.770	1.02	0.92	1.13	0.684	1.04	0.93	1.15	0.505	0.99	0.89	1.10	0.841
	Del	1.23	1.06	1.44	0.008	1.21	1.02	1.44	0.027	1.28	1.05	1.56	0.014	1.20	1.04	1.38	0.011
Season#	ANC	1.14	0.76	1.71	0.514	1.15	0.76	1.74	0.517	1.21	0.80	1.83	0.378	1.26	0.84	1.90	0.267
	Del	2.96	1.25	6.99	0.013	2.65	1.12	6.27	0.026	2.97	1.19	7.42	0.020	2.43	1.07	5.49	0.033
IPTp-SP doses	Del	1.07	0.77	1.51	0.678	1.32	0.88	1.98	0.178	1.46	0.91	2.36	0.119	1.14	0.82	1.57	0.436
AL	Del	0.72	0.48	1.08	0.108	0.83	0.53	1.29	0.406	0.70	0.43	1.12	0.137	0.75	0.51	1.11	0.150
Visit	ANC & Del*	2.43	1.68	3.50	0.000	2.68	1.79	4.03	0.000	3.11	2.04	4.75	0.000	2.22	1.55	3.18	0.000
	ANC & GP**	1.02	0.76	1.36	0.912	1.00	0.74	1.35	0.996	0.94	0.70	1.26	0.673	0.89	0.67	1.20	0.455

<i>dhps</i>		S436				A437			
Fixed effect(s)	Samples	OR	[95% CI]		<i>p</i>	OR	[95%CI]		<i>p</i>
Age (per 10 years)	ANC	1.28	0.91	1.80	0.162	0.89	0.62	1.28	0.533
	Del	1.13	0.69	1.86	0.619	0.79	0.39	1.58	0.501
	GP	1.01	0.89	1.15	0.844	1.21	1.05	1.40	0.009
Parasitaemia (log scale)	ANC	1.01	0.80	1.29	0.916	0.96	0.74	1.24	0.756
	Del	0.99	0.76	1.27	0.910	0.87	0.61	1.22	0.416
	GP	0.92	0.74	1.15	0.486	0.90	0.72	1.12	0.340
Gravity	ANC	1.04	0.94	1.15	0.479	0.99	0.89	1.10	0.880
	Del	1.02	0.88	1.18	0.757	0.99	0.81	1.22	0.948
Season#	ANC	1.51	1.00	2.30	0.051	0.75	0.48	1.17	0.204
	Del	1.43	0.57	3.58	0.446	1.17	0.35	3.96	0.800
IPTp-SP doses	Del	0.92	0.66	1.29	0.633	1.63	0.94	2.83	0.080
AL	Del	0.93	0.62	1.39	0.710	0.68	0.41	1.11	0.122
Visit	ANC & Del*	1.87	1.14	3.07	0.014	2.72	1.71	4.33	0.000
	ANC & GP**	0.76	0.57	1.02	0.071	0.74	0.54	1.01	0.057

Del = delivery; AL = artemether-lumefantrine therapy #dry season = 0, rainy season = 1; *ANC booking = 0, Delivery = 1; **ANC booking = 0, GP = 1